

Training for research data management: comparative European approaches

Report from a Knowledge Exchange survey and workshop

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1 Introduction and key findings

1.1. In today's changing research environment, there is a need for researchers at all stages in their careers, along with research support staff, to nurture their skills and knowhow in the management of research data. Promoting the openness and re-use of research data is one of the principal aims of the **Knowledge Exchange (KE) partnership**¹. At the end of 2015, KE initiated a project to compare approaches in research data management (RDM) training within the partnership's five member countries. The project was structured around two strands of activity:

- ▶ **A survey** to collect information on current practice around RDM training, in order to provide an overview of the RDM training landscape
- ▶ **A workshop** to share successful approaches to RDM training and capacity building provided within institutions and by infrastructure; the workshop took place in London on 9-10 February 2016

1.2. RDM, as covered in the project, comprises the different components of the research data lifecycle, from data creation to data preserving, sharing and re-use. But as the workshop discussion made clear, RDM is an integral part of the wider research process, contributing the standards and principles of research, and applicable not just to the research data lifecycle, but throughout the lifecycle of research projects as a whole. RDM skills and training thus form a necessary component of the broader professional development of researchers and other professional groups that support researchers.

1.3. Moreover, RDM skills apply to all disciplines. The survey responses emphasise the extent to which the training effort is spread evenly over the range of broad subject areas. And it also relates to all stages of research careers, from PhD students onwards, as well as to research support professions such as librarians and research administrators. It follows that the relevance of RDM skills is widely applicable, and the potential audiences for RDM training correspondingly large.

1.4. This report describes the outputs of the project. It is in two parts: **section 2** provides an analysis of the survey (details about the data underpinning the survey can be found at **paragraph 2.2**), and **section 3** is a report from the workshop itself. The document therefore provides an evidence base and informed suggestions to help improve RDM training practices KE partner countries and beyond.

Key findings and conclusions

1.5. The survey results point to areas where particular factors dominate the responses:

- ▶ Training materials are very largely geared for universities, faculties and departments
- ▶ PhD students are recipients of almost all the training, although not exclusively so
- ▶ A preponderant amount of the training is not focused on any particular type of data
- ▶ Virtually all phases of the research data lifecycle are well covered by the training endeavour
- ▶ Almost all of the training is provided either wholly or partly on site, face-to-face
- ▶ Data curators and data librarians are the main group that delivers the training, but researchers themselves are also responsible for much of the delivery
- ▶ The number of individuals who have received training since 2014 is relatively low for most organisations
- ▶ Awareness building is seen as by far the biggest perceived impact of the training

1.6. At the same time, the results do not reveal strong correlations between the different factors. Thus for the most part, there appears to be no relationship, for instance, between the discipline of those being trained, the environment in which they are located and the scope and nature of the training. In further questions, the type of training evaluation is not associated with any particular sort of training impact; and the growing interest in training is not reflected by the relatively small numbers of individuals who have actually taken part in RDM training since 2014.

1.7. The survey also throws up some interesting disassociations, notably between learning objectives on the one hand, and training strengths or impact on the other. In these instances, there are surprisingly weak associations between what is set out as an objective, and with what is actually achieved in practice.

1.8. The workshop discussions addressed a number of broad questions:

- ▶ How to develop among researchers, and others, an awareness of RDM training needs
- ▶ Means of measuring the success and impact of training interventions, along with changes in practice and behaviour
- ▶ The challenges associated with the successful implementation of training initiatives
- ▶ The role of different categories of players, other than researchers themselves, notably research administrators, records managers and archivists, learned and professional bodies, and research funders

1.9. Elaborating on these questions, the discussions considered what might be done, practically, to make training more relevant to the professional lives of researchers, and to encourage good RDM practice with a view to effecting behavioural and cultural change. Suggestions included:

- ▶ Providing incentives for training, professional development and good practice from research funders, learned / professional bodies and publishers
- ▶ Charting the RDM capabilities of universities
- ▶ Identifying the RDM roles of key professional groups
- ▶ Engaging with learned / professional bodies to assess whether and how their policies and practices relate to RDM
- ▶ Investigating the potential for a sustainable registry of information on training resources

Footnotes

- 1** Knowledge Exchange (KE) partnership
<http://www.knowledge-exchange.info>
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2 Survey analysis

2.1. The survey consisted of 24 questions, carefully worded to elicit a broad picture of the scope, manifestations and characteristics of RDM training in KE partner countries. Nineteen of these questions offered multiple tick-box response options; three required open-ended responses in key areas: perceived strengths of the training endeavour, impact of the training and what might be improved in training provision; and the remaining two questions asked respondents to provide additional information on their resources. Following the dissemination of the questionnaire, a total of 118 responses were received during December 2015 and January 2016, **from across all five KE partner countries (figure 1)** – although the national spread of responses is not even, with over half of them from Germany alone, and significantly smaller proportions from the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Finland and Denmark. One response was also received from each of four non-KE partner countries: France, Greece, Norway and Switzerland. Fifteen of the respondents were discounted because they did not go beyond questions 1 or 2. The analysis therefore relates just to the remaining 103 sets of responses.

2.2. The remainder of this section is a detailed description and analysis of each set of responses. **Full response data** can be found at **Annex A**. The initial questions are broadly contextual, relating to the environments where training takes place, the audiences and the coverage of the training. In addition, the **raw data**, in Excel spreadsheets, is also available².

2.3. The **disciplinary subject coverage** of the training effort is broad (**figure 2**): life sciences, humanities/social sciences and natural sciences are all represented equally, accounting for around a fifth of respondents each. However, much the bigger proportion, around a third, is for general training which is not subject specific. Not surprisingly, such general training is not associated with any particular type of data, as outlined at 2.8 below.

Figure 1: Location of respondents' countries

Figure 2: Disciplinary subject for which RDM training is provided

Footnotes

- 2 The raw data is accessible at http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/13/KE_Training_%26_Skills_Survey_Dec_2015_Raw_data_-_all_responses.xlsx
A tidied up version of this, including additional analytical data drawn from some of the responses (and described where appropriate in this report) is accessible at http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/14/KE_Training_%26_Skills_Survey_Dec_2015_Tidied_data_-_individual_responses.xlsx
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.51348

2.4. Training takes place in different types of organisation

(figure 4), but a large majority of respondents provide their training materials for universities: almost 60% according to the survey, but arguably, this figure is nearer to 70%, if it is combined with the respondents who provide training in faculties/departments – which, it may be assumed, are all part of universities. In addition, 30% provide training material geared to research organisations – but almost none of that is related to training that is general and non-subject specific. In this area, the training is clearly destined for specific subject areas, with a fairly even spread across humanities/social sciences, life sciences and natural sciences.

2.5. A notable proportion of respondents, 28%, offer training open to any organisation. Accordingly, two thirds of those respondents provide training materials destined for five or more types of audience – the wider spread of audiences reflecting the degree of openness. Conversely, fewer than 8% provide training for learned societies or discipline-specific organisation.

2.6. The number of target audiences (figure 4) that are the recipients of training is wide-ranging, with each respondent reaching out to a mean average of 4.3 different audiences out of a possible 11 categories. Almost half of respondents offer courses to five or more audiences; conversely, only 16% offer courses to two or fewer.

2.7. It is striking that a near totality of respondents provides training for PhD students. Senior researchers/postdocs and graduate students also account for well over half of

the audiences. The training effort is thus concentrated very heavily on postgraduate students and established academics. At a more senior level, professors are also significant recipients of training, and almost all respondents who provide training for senior researchers also do so for professors. But undergraduates are much less well represented among training recipients, as are the non-academic audiences: librarians, data curators and IT departments/computer centres are catered for by a third or less of respondents. The general public represents only a small proportion of training recipients; just a tenth of respondents (mostly among those who target larger numbers of audiences) choose to offer courses to that category.

Figure 3: Types of organisation for which RDM training is provided

Figure 4: Target audience for RDM training

2.8. With regards to **types of data** covered by the training (**figure 5**), respondents report a fairly generic approach: two thirds of respondents state that their training does not focus on any particular type. Where there is a particular focus, the training tends to relate to data in the form of numbers, text and images. Overall, only 12% of respondents offer training relating to just one of these three types of data, suggesting a degree of diversification in the training offer.

2.9. Almost all respondents who offer training specifically in the humanities/social sciences also have a focus that includes text-based data. And with only a couple of exceptions, those offering life sciences or natural sciences training have a focus that either includes numbers-based data, or that has no particular focus at all. The 'other data type' category relates generally to a range of specialist data types, including for instance mass spectrometry and sequencing data (DNA, nucleotide, molecular); tabular data is also referred to in a few cases.

2.10. Another way of ascertaining the scope of the training is to examine the **phases of the data lifecycle** that it addresses (**figure 6**). Responses to this question pointed to a very broad offer by respondents, with almost half of them providing training that covers all phases of the lifecycle. There are eight specific phases flagged up by the questionnaire, and for no fewer than seven of these, training is provided by a quarter or more of respondents. Only a small proportion of respondents offer training that does not focus primarily on the data lifecycle.

Figure 5: Types of data that is the focus of RDM training

Figure 6: Phases of the research data lifecycle covered by RDM training

2.11. Among those respondents that do not address all phases of the data lifecycle (or that do not address the lifecycle at all), there is much breadth in the number of phases addressed by training, with a mean average of 4.3 phases covered. 47% offer training in five or more phases, with just 15% doing so for one or two phases only.

2.12. Two media largely dominate the **way that training material is presented (figure 7)**: almost all respondents use slides and/or different sorts of digital format – although printed material remains an important medium too, used by almost half; in a large majority of cases, respondents use them as well as slides and digital formats. Video, including YouTube, is rather more prevalent than audio only (e.g. recorded talk). Over a fifth report the use of other types of material, with more than half of these involving some sort of face-to-face interaction such as workshops, interactive exercises and hands-on training.

2.13. As for the **format of the training (figure 8)**, almost all respondents make use of on-site, hands-on training; two-thirds use only this approach, and a further 28% make use of both on-site and web-based training (via Skype, YouTube or other web-based interfaces).

2.14. Openness of resources is an important factor for most respondents; over half of them report that their training material is **freely available on the Internet (figure 9)**, with only a fifth saying that the material can only be accessed for a fee. A further fifth don't know whether or not their organisations' material is freely available. There is no particular relationship between the openness and the type of material, as reported at 2.12 above.

Figure 7: Type of RDM training material

Figure 8: Format of RDM training material

Figure 9: Free availability of RDM training material on the Internet

2.15. Over half of respondents report that their training addresses **applications dedicated to working with data (figure 10)**. Of those that indicated which applications are used, over half confirmed the deployment of DMP-related tools, notably DMPonline. The range of other tools is wide; with the exception of BExIS (used in biodiversity research), no single tool is cited by more than one respondent.

2.16. A large majority of respondents report that the **training timeframe (figure 11)** is relatively short, spread over either one or two days: almost half organise one-day workshops, over a fifth opt for block lectures or similar approaches over two days. But in reality, the figure is even higher: of those respondents who indicate 'other' in their responses, around half report training sessions lasting just a few hours. The proportion of respondents offering training over no more than a day thus goes up to around two thirds. Other specified timeframes (summer schools or similar events over more than two days, self-paced training and weekly sessions in a term) are deployed in roughly similar numbers:.. Included within the 'other' category, 15% of respondents offer courses for a number of hours at given intervals of time.

2.17. The most important **deliverers of training (figure 12)** are data curators/data librarians, as reported by over half of respondents. It is worth noting that in almost half of those cases – for 24% of respondents overall – they are the sole professional groups who deliver the training. Researchers themselves also account for a significant proportion of the training delivery, as reported by 44%; they are the sole professional group delivering the training in less than a third of those cases, amounting to 13% of all respondents. Administrators and staff based in computing/data centres each account for a little under a third of responses.

2.18. Training appears to be largely a focused responsibility within each organisation. In almost half of the cases, or 48%, training is delivered by just one of the professional groups listed. Conversely, only 13% report that training is undertaken by three or more of these groups.

Figure 10: Whether RDM training address applications dedicated to working with data (DMP-tool, visualisation tool, etc.)

Figure 11: Typical time frame of RDM training

Figure 12: Who delivers RDM training

2.19. Training tends to address a multiplicity of **learning objectives (figure 13)**. Of the seven objectives in the questionnaire, five are flagged as relevant by over half of respondents. Almost all of these recognise improved knowledge and understanding as a major learning objective; this is followed by changing practice and/or behaviour, skills acquisition, influencing attitudes and values application awareness-building. Recognition levels are somewhat lower for the remaining two factors, application literacy and helping with career progression.

2.20. It is instructive to compare the learning objectives with the perceived strengths and impact of the training effort, as discussed at 2.27 to 2.29. In a couple of cases, the factors are similar – and where they are, there is a dissociation between learning objectives on the one hand, and training strengths or impact on the other.

- ▶ Of those respondents listing changes in practice and behaviour as an important learning objective, only a fifth identify improved behaviour, attitude or practices as a positive impact of the training
- ▶ Of those respondents listing the acquisition of skills as an important learning objective, fewer than a third identify the imparting of practical skills as a strength of their training effort

For the other factors relating to learning objectives, there is less of a match with those relating to strength and impact of the training, and it is therefore more difficult to draw inferences.

2.21. The overall **number of training recipients** is relatively small across respondents' organisations (**figure 14**). Almost three quarters of respondents report that fewer than 200 people have taken part in training since 2014. In a third of cases, fewer than 50 recipients have benefited. Conversely, only a tiny proportion applies to training that has been attended by 500 or more people. For almost a tenth of respondents, training has either not yet started, or the number of recipients is unknown. Under two thirds of respondents report a **growing interest in training (figure 15)**. There is no obvious correlation between the level of interest and the number of individuals taking part in training sessions.

Figure 13: Main learning objectives of RDM training

Figure 14: Number of participants who have taken part in RDM training since 2014

Figure 15: Whether there is a growing interest in training

2.22. The survey suggests six groups of **stakeholders interested in receiving training (figure 16a)**. Such interest does not appear to extend to a multiplicity of audience in each institution or organisation: for 64% of respondents, just one or two such audiences expressed an interest. In only 8% of cases was there recorded interest from four or more audiences.

2.23. Researchers and senior researchers are by some stretch the group that expresses the most interest in receiving training. They are followed by undergraduates and graduates, staff based in research offices of special departments/units, librarians and staff based in computer/data centres. PhD students do not appear as a distinct category for this question. However, these are signalled as the key interested group by about half of respondents who listed 'other' in response to the question.

2.24. It is instructive to compare the responses to this question with those relating to target audiences for training materials, as set out in figure 3 and at 2.6 - 2.7 (**figure 16b**). The categories are not identical (as noted above, PhD students are not specifically included in figure 15a), but it is possible to draw comparisons by merging different groups – for instance, in figure 3, undergraduates and graduates are listed separately, but they are brought together in figure 15a. For all categories, the proportion of individuals who form the target audience is invariably higher than those who have expressed an interest in training. The discrepancy is widest among the undergraduates/

graduates group, where respondents indicate that 63% are a target audience, but only 46% express a particular interest in training. Conversely, there is less of a difference for staff based in research offices of special departments/units: they are a target for 36% of respondents, and 31% are reported to express an interest in training. It is difficult to draw inferences, but it is nevertheless striking that there is a systematic discrepancy between trainers' expectations and the feelings expressed by those being trained.

Figure 16a: Stakeholders who are especially interested in being trained

Figure 16b: Comparison between target audiences for training materials and stakeholders particularly interested in RDM training

Figure 17: Ways in which RDM training is evaluated

2.25. The completion of questionnaires is reported as the most frequent type of **training evaluation (figure 17)**, by 42% of respondents, with a split of 27% for printed questionnaires and 15% for online ones. The recording of personal feedback is flagged up by a third of respondents. However, a notable proportion of them do not undertake any evaluation at all. The survey questions did not allow for a consideration of how longer-term outcomes and impact might be evaluated; this was the focus of much discussion during the 9-10 February workshop – see 3.13 to 3.17 below.

2.26. The next three questions in the survey called for open-ended responses. These yielded a richer seam of information, with a wide variety of views expressed. To help with the analysis, a number of broad themes were identified and extrapolated from each set of responses; they are set out as additional data, to provide a degree of categorisation for the disparate views expressed. Inevitably, these themes overlap to an extent, and given the brevity (and in some cases, lack of clarity) of many responses, there is some subjectivity about the most appropriate theme(s) used to describe the views articulated by respondents.

2.27. Strengths of the training (figure 18): almost two thirds of respondents gave answers to this question, although some of these were not specific. Nevertheless, there is a trend from the feedback, with the imparting of practical skills and the raising of awareness perceived as the two dominant strengths of the training effort. In descending order, other strengths were providing expert

Figure 18: Perceived strengths of RDM training

advice, ability to tailor the training to user needs, promoting relationships and networking among training recipients, understanding RDM principles and theory, and quality of the teaching.

- ▶ Imparting practical skills is deemed by over a third of respondents to be a strength of their training endeavour. Many of them talk about the importance of hands-on approaches, (the term ‘hands-on’ recurs frequently), including the use of exercises. They also underline the need to address concrete problems or to help trainees with the use of specific resources, tools, applications or systems; and in the deployment of good practices, such as data citation
- ▶ Raising awareness of the importance and relevance of RDM, and of good practice, is seen as another important strength, by nearly a third. There is an emphasis here on such factors as highlighting the benefits of RDM and generally getting a better understanding of how this fits in with the research process
- ▶ Almost a quarter cite the provision of expert advice as a key strength of the training. This is associated with making trainees aware of where to go, within their organisations, to seek such advice or assistance. Some respondents underline the experts’ breadth of experience, their capacity to address practical challenges faced by researchers, their ability to act as advisors for particular projects or even project proposals (associated with tailoring to need, as outlined below)

- ▶ The ability to tailor the training to user needs is cited by 16%, either in the context of courses themselves, or through bespoke advice or support in practical settings. There is some emphasis on the value of collaborative working between the trainees and trainers
- ▶ Other strength factors are cited less frequently by respondents: promoting or encouraging relationships and networking among training recipients; understanding RDM principles and/or theory; and for a very small number, a clear reference has been made to the quality of the teaching (although it is recognised that this may be inherent in other responses, but has not been flagged up so explicitly)
- ▶ Finally, 14% did not identify any particular strengths in the training
- ▶ The building of awareness of, or sensitivity to RDM, its benefits and the importance of good practice, is flagged up by two fifths of respondents. Some point to raised awareness among particular training recipients, such as PhD students; others underline how awareness matters in particular to certain stages of the research lifecycle or to particular activities associated with research data. However, most respondents provide fairly general and non-specific views of increased awareness
- ▶ Some way behind, almost a fifth point to positive changes in RDM practices. But whereas awareness-building is perceived in broad, general terms, the responses often associate improvement in with particular aspects of RDM; examples listed include data management planning, use of software tools, use of standards, preparation of research data submitted to repositories and attentiveness to legal requirements

2.28. Impact of the training (figure 19): this is a crucial question, since the responses encapsulate the ability of the training endeavour to improve the RDM skills of the research community. As noted at 2.25, impact does not really feature as a factor for training evaluation, so the responses here provide potentially valuable insights into the usefulness of the training. One particular factor dominates: the building of awareness of RDM is seen by far as the biggest impact of the training. Changes in practice, a greater visibility for data services and changes in behaviour and/or attitude follow some way behind.

- ▶ An increased visibility of data services (including the availability of data repositories), of the expertise that they provide and who to turn to for help, is cited as a positive impact by 12% of respondents
- ▶ Changes in behaviour and/or attitudes might be deemed to be inherent to better awareness or changes in practices, but that factor is highlighted specifically by over 8%. This is associated for instance with greater acceptance of data sharing and willingness to educate themselves more in RDM (and by the same token, spread the knowledge to their colleagues)

Figure 19: Impact of RDM training

- ▶ The building of networks, contacts and relationships between individuals interested in RDM is a relatively factor, recognised by 7% of respondents
- ▶ A notable proportion of respondents – just over a fifth – point to a general and positive impact of the training, but without being more specific
- ▶ Finally, 7% of respondents claim that there has been little, insufficient or no impact; and a tenth say that they either don't know, or it is too early to say
- ▶ There is a widespread interest in seeing more training focused on particular factors: 22% call for training in the use of specific tools, applications and methods; 20% for training tailored for specific disciplines (although the subject areas themselves are not specified in the responses); 17% for training on particular topics (examples given include the data lifecycle, RDM concepts, privacy/data protection/legal issues, versioning, file structures...); 7% for training geared to researchers at given career stages; and 2% for training on particular data types

2.29. It is interesting that almost half of respondents who indicated, in figure 16, that they do not evaluate their training nevertheless provided some information about impact. Generally, there is no apparent correlation between the type of training evaluation and the nature of the recorded impact.

2.30. Areas for improvement (figure 20): this question has yielded a rather long wish list of suggestions where no particular factor dominates. Indeed, some of the suggestions are very specific.

- ▶ Under a third of respondents indicate that they wish to see improvements in approaches to training and teaching, including the way that tutorials or sessions are run, the nature of training materials (for instance, through the greater use of video, which several respondents highlighted), the introduction of more interactivity, the use of hands-on approaches (also suggested by several
- ▶ A small number of respondents, just under 6%, would like to see improvements in their organisations' data infrastructure: improving the tools needed to administer data, greater expertise in key areas and better means for finding data
- ▶ 6% feel that improvements are needed in all areas, and conversely, the same number believe few or no improvements are required

Figure 20: Areas for improvement

2.31. The **types of organisation that are responsible for the training (figure 21)** mirror, to an extent, the organisations for which training is provided, as outlined in figure 2. Not surprisingly, universities are by far both the main providers and recipients, for around 60% of respondents. In about 30% of cases, it is research organisations that provide and receive the training.

2.32. Conversely, there is an apparent discrepancy between some of the types of organisation and the professional groups that deliver the training. Figure 21 shows that almost 22% of the training is provided by libraries, but the responses described by figure 11 indicate that in 58% of cases, the training is delivered by data librarians or data curators; it may be that much of that higher proportion is attributed, in figure 21, to universities rather than libraries. There is a similar pattern with computing centres: these account for just 8% of responses in figure 21, whereas in figure 11, 29% of respondents say that staff based in computing or data centres are responsible for delivering the training.

2.33. The final factor considered by the survey is **the number of years that organisations have been involved in training (figure 22)**. For many, RDM training is a well-established activity: in nearly 29% of cases, this has been provided for five or more years. But it is also true that, in around half of cases, respondents' organisations have delivered training for three or fewer years. There is no obvious relationship between the extent to which the training endeavour is established and the number of individuals actually being trained. Even where RDM training has been a feature for five or more years, around half of respondents report levels of participation of under 200 since 2014. Longevity of training resources is thus not a guarantee of increased take-up by users.

2.34. The survey provides valuable information on a variety of practices and attributes associated with training in RDM. However, the results do not reveal strong correlations between the different factors; indeed, the absence of discernible associations is a striking feature in itself. Thus for the most part, there appears to be no relationship, for instance, between the discipline of those being trained, the environment in which they are located and the scope and nature of the training; the notable exception to this is a certain association between subject discipline the type of data that is the focus of the training, as

outlined at 2.9. Indeed, in some cases, the apparent absence of any association raises questions. Thus for instance, the type of training evaluation is not associated with any particular sort of impact (perhaps not surprising since, as noted, the evaluation methods picked up by the survey do not seem geared to address longer-term outcomes and impact). And the growing interest in training is not reflected by the relatively small numbers of individuals who have actually taken part in RDM training since 2014.

Figure 21: Type of organisation that respondents work for or that are responsible for RDM training

Figure 22: Number of years that respondents' organisations have been involved in delivering RDM training

2.35. Around a third of the questions elicit responses that are dominated by one particular factor, including notably:

- ▶ Training materials are very largely geared for universities, faculties and departments
- ▶ PhD students are recipients of almost all the training, although not exclusively so
- ▶ A preponderant amount of the training is not focused on any particular type of data
- ▶ Virtually all phases of the research data lifecycle are well covered by the training endeavour
- ▶ Almost all of the training is provided either wholly or partly on site, face-to-face
- ▶ Data curators and data librarians are the main group that delivers the training, but researchers themselves are also responsible for much of the delivery
- ▶ The number of individuals who have received training since 2014 is relatively low for most organisations
- ▶ Awareness-building dominates as the biggest perceived impact of the training

2.36. The survey also points to a few disassociations, as outlined at 2.20: a misalignment between some of the learning objectives, and corresponding impact or perceived strengths; and a proportion of those targeted for training which is invariably greater than those who express a particular interest in the training.

3 Workshop

3.1. The workshop took place in London, on 9-10 February 2016. Its aim was to share successful approaches to RDM training and capacity building provided within institutions and by infrastructure providers in the five KE partner countries. The event provided an opportunity for:

- ▶ Sharing of experiences, key challenges and lessons learned with regards to successful approaches to RDM training and capacity building
- ▶ Discussing success criteria for training approaches and how successful approaches and examples of good practice might be replicated in other countries
- ▶ Identifying gaps in terms of training provision and capacity building and discussing possible solutions how these could be addressed

The **list of workshop participants** is at [Annex B](#).

3.2. Around 30 individuals took part in the workshop representing research data support staff responsible for overseeing, planning, designing and delivering RDM training in all KE partner countries. The event was articulated around:

- ▶ Eight presentations describing the practices and experiences of a variety of RDM training initiatives in the KE partner countries, along with a presentation of the results of the survey; the **resources covered by the presentations** are listed at [Annex C](#)
- ▶ Two discussion sessions, in break-out groups, to consider lessons learnt, examples of good practice, impact of RDM training, training success criteria and challenges and steps towards successful training

A brief outline of each presentation is set out below, followed by a synthesis of the two discussion sessions and conclusions reached.

Presentations

3.3. Ellen Verbakel, Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), **The Essentials 4 Data Support Course**³: this is offered by Research Data Netherlands, is a collaborative venture between 3TU.Datacentrum, DANS and SURF. The research lifecycle is used as a framework for the course, which is offered in three formats: online only (without registration), online only with user profile and as a full course (online + face-to-face with certificate – run at least twice a year). The online resources place much emphasis on visual/audio-visual material, as participants have suggested that they prefer approaches that are not too text-rich. The material available freely in both Dutch and English.

3.4. Jonas Recker, GESIS Data Archive for the Social Sciences (Germany), **CESSDA training – RDM training in the social sciences**⁴: Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives (CESSDA), targets its RDM training at PhD students and early career researchers; no prior knowledge of RDM is assumed. Training takes the form of 2-day workshops made up of eight 90-minute sessions; sessions typically cater for 12-20 participants. There have been 19 workshops since 2012 mostly in English, some in German. Many topics, such as data storage and data security, are not specific to the social sciences; but others are, notably consent/ethics and anonymization. Participants report a high demand for guidance on informed consent, anonymization/data protection and IPR. Challenges include accommodating heterogeneous groups of participants who deploy different research approaches; face-to-face workshops don't scale, so other forms of training are necessary to meet demand; and finding a balance between theory and practice.

Footnotes

- ³ The Essentials 4 Data Support Course
http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/8/E4DS_Ellen_Verbakel.pptx
 - ⁴ CESSDA training – RDM training in the social sciences
http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/6/RDM_Training_in_the_Social_Sciences_Jonas_Recker.pdf
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3.5. Libby Bishop, UK Data Service (United Kingdom), **A decade of research data management – What have we learned?**⁵: UKDA benefits from having strong research experience among its trainers; this gives it the ability to speak the language of researchers. It also has strong institutional support from the relevant research funder (ESRC). And UKDA works with real data, so there is a strong practical bias to the training effort, based on reality – workshops are customised to participants' backgrounds and projects. All training material is freely available, including the use of exercises drawn from real-life case studies. Challenges include: how to make use of The Cloud for collaborative research; encryption; data sharing and the extent to which curation is required; allowing for more and more exercises; learning by doing; dealing with new and novel data.

3.6. Gareth Knight, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom), **RDM training for health researchers**⁶: the presentations described an institutional perspective for health researchers. Drivers at LSHTM include ensuring compliance (for instance, with data security/confidentiality), improving funding prospects and enhancing research practice. The latter is quite domain-specific and can be challenging. The training offer is varied: research degree modules, online courses, sharing resources with other neighbouring institutions, ad hoc lunchtime events, talent and educational development for staff. Forty different courses available in all. Most training focuses on the early stages of research: principles, capture, analysis...

3.7. Joy Davidson, Digital Curation Centre (United Kingdom), **Train the trainers – lessons learnt as part of the DCC institutional engagement work**⁷: DCC has organised 60 'training the trainers' events which have attracted 3,500 participants. Training audiences include library staff, research administrators, IT staff and project. But some target groups are missing at this stage: archivists/ records managers, finance teams, legal officers, data protection/FoI staff, ethics teams and staff involved in discipline-specific support. For all these groups, it is important to convey why RDM matters and how it relates to their areas of competence. Topics covered in the training include the entire research data lifecycle, specific use of RDM tools (such as DPM Online) and generic vs. specific discipline approaches. There are also gaps in coverage, notably dealing with non-digital data, costing RDM and

intermediate and advanced level training, to ensure that trainers do not fall behind the developing RDM capacity of researchers. These training expectations nevertheless need to be balanced with the reality on the ground: most HEIs have fewer than two dedicated staff members in data management posts. These tend to be spread across the institution (library, IT department, research office...). Training opportunities might be better exploited by:

- ▶ Reducing the training burden by blending general training from external providers such as DCC and UKDS with locale-specific resources
- ▶ Exploring partnerships with European Research Infrastructures, such as ERICS, in developing discipline-specific and infrastructure-specific training
- ▶ Setting up buddying system with more 'mature' institutions

A longer term view requires the development of methods and approaches to track impact. The benefits include compliance with funders' requirements, systems and support that are utilised and relevant to researchers' needs, better/more reproducible research, more visible research outputs and easier reporting through more joined-up systems.

Footnotes

- 5 A decade of research data management – What have we learned? http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/1/A_decade_of_RDM_What_have_we_learned_Libby_Bishop.pptx
 - 6 RDM training for health researchers http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/9/RDM_Training_for_Health_Researchers_Gareth_Knight.pptx
 - 7 Train the trainers – lessons learnt as part of the DCC institutional engagement work http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/11/Training_the_Trainers%2C_lessons_learned_Joy_Davidson.pptx
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3.8. Henrik Pedersen, University of Southern Denmark, **Data management – Working with the researchers in Denmark**⁸: the presentation provided a run-down on the Danish national context, where a National Forum for RDM brings together eight universities, the Royal Library, the State Library and the National Archive. The vision is to endow Danish universities with a consistent set of RDM policies by 2018; and to ensure that the landscape of infrastructures for the research data lifecycles is properly understood. In the short term, it is important to provide support for researchers, notably with regards to data management planning, with a view to deliver sample DMPs for different disciplines by mid-2016. In the longer term, disciplinary requirements can be looked at in greater detail, focusing on factors such as storage solutions, computing needs and DOIs.

3.9. Karsten Kryger Hansen, Aalborg University Library (Denmark), **Marketing and training toolkit in Denmark**⁹: the presentation describes a project whose purpose is to develop a toolkit to facilitate training and information for researchers. The toolkit will involve the creation of information material, guides, training material and course material. There will be information campaigns at Danish universities to spread knowledge of the solutions provided by the project, with an emphasis on making templates for courses in RDM targeted at PhD students. Creating the toolkit requires looking at the context where RDM is taught, including academic disciplines, as well as the time necessary for both preparation and participation, level of knowledge, academic approaches and educational techniques. This should provide the basis for deriving a flexible curriculum that is capable of meeting the diverse needs of users. The curriculum should thereby encompass key focal points: perspectives (for instance, reproducibility vs. re-usability, research integrity), various levels of learning objectives, inspiration for active learning, bank of materials, syllabus, discipline-specific subjects of interest and factsheets. The platform for the toolkit will be a wiki or knowledge base, using either MediaWiki or WordPress, with API based access to information. In the overall vision for the toolkit, teaching will be relatively minor in comparison with the development of RDM support functions.

3.10. Christian Jämsen, National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) (Finland), **Data Policy in the National Institute for Health, training workshops and possibilities of Finnish data**¹⁰: THL collects patient data, by definition of a sensitive nature, across 16 thematic registries, to monitor the health of the Finnish population and to provide material for researchers. But although this represents a huge trove of data, many researchers are not properly aware of the contents – so there is a task to promote the data. This implies the need to find out what researchers and other users want, and to manage the data effectively so that it is made available in timely fashion and in usable (customisable) formats. THL's data policy is based on a five-point plan: making datasets visible, improving timeliness and custom reporting, making open data, making datasets available and adopting electronic data lifecycle management.

3.11. Finally, there was also a presentation from Stéphane Goldstein, InformAll (United Kingdom), on the **Results of the Knowledge Exchange survey of training and skills in research data management**¹¹. This described the highlights of the survey covered in detail in section 2 of this report.

Footnotes

- 8** Data management – Working with the researchers in Denmark http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/7/RDM_Working_with_Researchers_in_Denmark_Henrik_Pedersen.pptx
 - 9** Marketing and training toolkit in Denmark http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/3/Marketing_%26_Training_Toolkit_in_Denmark_Karsten_Kryger_Hansen.pptx
 - 10** Data Policy in the National Institute for Health, training workshops and possibilities of Finnish data http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/10/Reliable_Information_for_use_in_decision_making_%26_work_in_social_and_health_care_Christian_Jamsen.pptx
 - 11** Results of the Knowledge Exchange survey of training and skills in research data management http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/15/Presentation_Results_of_the_KE_survey_of_training_and_skills_in_RDM_-_InformAll.pptx
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Synthesis of the two discussion sessions

Developing an awareness of training needs

3.12. Assessment of training needs of users (i.e. research students and researchers) in RDM is desirable in any organisational setting, but is difficult in practice. It is not undertaken systematically by trainers; tellingly, the survey did not include a question on needs assessment.

Researchers tend not to perceive a need for training – except when driven by the data management requirements, mandates or expectations of funders. In such cases, the incentive for training follows pragmatically from an imperative just to meet basic requirements, rather than by an earnest desire on their part to improve research and/or data management practice.

3.13. But this is not sufficient; deploying good RDM should be seen as more than just an additional means of securing funding or ensuring compliance with requirements. It should be recognised as an integral (and perhaps even a mandatory) part of the research process, close to the working experiences of researchers and applicable throughout the lifecycle of research projects, and not just for drawing data management plans. It should also be seen as contributing to the standards and principles of research, and to the professionalism of researchers – Vitae’s Researcher Development Framework (RDF), and particularly its **information literacy lens**¹², is an example of a professional/career development tool which addresses data management and curation competencies. A starting point for any training strategy is therefore to make researchers realise that RDM is both professionally relevant and important. There may be a case for codes of conduct to underline this. National strategies may be needed to achieve this, involving the marketing of RDM within institutions, with a recognised body taking the lead. As outlined in the presentations from Joy Davidson and Henrik Pedersen (see 3.7 and 3.8), the UK and Denmark have in place organisations that, in some RDM areas at least, do have a national, strategic role. However, it has been recognised that approaches would be different for small and larger countries.

Measuring success, demonstrating impact

3.14. Evaluation and following-up on the training effort are critically important, to provide the evidence that helps inform criteria for future training. As demonstrated by the survey, evaluation tends to focus on shorter-term

outcomes, typically drawn from questionnaires filled at the end of courses. The success of training may be gauged in terms of attainment of learning objectives; but this implies longer-term follow-up, beyond immediate post-training evaluation. As part of this, training recipients might be asked what they see have achieved in practice on the basis of training needs that they themselves have defined; how confident they have become; what value they believe they derived from the training; but also what obstacles they might have encountered in seeking to apply what they have learnt.

3.15. Success may also be demonstrated by ascertaining longer-term impact, as characterised by changes in the practice, behaviour and confidence of individuals who have gone through relevant training, and more broadly by changes in research culture. The measurement of change is difficult, but may be achieved quantitatively through initially laying down benchmarks and then deploying metrics, relating to factors such as:

- ▶ Number of datasets deposited
- ▶ Use/re-use/reproducibility of data; re-use may increase data integrity, and by the same token, trust – but it is recognised that a capacity to measure re-use may be quite far down the road
- ▶ Take-up of data and associated data citation, including across disciplines

Such change may be monitored longitudinally, but also by comparing different institutions or departments. However, it should be remembered that training is not the only way of changing research culture; as suggested at 3.11, some disciplines and communities will only evolve if compelled by mandates from funders.

Footnotes

12 Information literacy lens

<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/vitae-publications/rdf-related/information-literacy-lens-on-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework-rdf-apr-2012.pdf/view>

3.16. Change may also be measured through approaches that are more qualitative, for instance by looking at:

- ▶ The confidence of researchers in managing data so as to reproduce their own research
- ▶ Researchers' improved metadata practices to enable more effective re-use and reproducibility
- ▶ The extent to which institutions recognise the need for good RDM, and accordingly recruit and deploy individuals to well-defined and visible support and training roles

3.17. More broadly, a further success criterion is the way that RDM practices can contribute to increase the integrity of research results and create new research opportunities, including across disciplines. There is a likely relationship between good data management and good science, and indicators of good science might be usefully gauged comparatively in settings where there is and isn't RDM training provision.

3.18. The identification of success stories and the sharing of good practice, as well as examples of how effective RDM can bring about tangible benefits, are good ways of illustrating the effectiveness of training – along with associated changes in behaviour. Success stories might demonstrate, for instance, where data sharing practices have led to significantly increased and beneficial re-use of data; and show how a better understanding of metadata can result in improved retrievability of research data. Researchers themselves might also be asked to provide testimonials and examples of success stories resulting from good RDM practice – such as whether the citation of their datasets has gone up as a result of greater data openness; the extent to which colleagues are turning to them for advice on research data; and whether they have become RDM champions (in this respect, it is noteworthy that, according to the survey results, researchers represent a significant proportion of trainers). Increasing the visibility of good practice could be beneficial as a means of increasing awareness, attracting interest and thereby further help to achieve recognition of training need; case studies could be put together and publicised, although this in itself may require much effort.

Challenges and how to address them

3.19. The success and impact of RDM training is largely dependent on addressing a number of interrelated challenges:

- ▶ Ensuring that the training is practical and relevant to users, taking account of their views. The use of examples and making users work with data during their training can help to building understanding and buy-in
- ▶ Addressing different levels of skill of those being trained
- ▶ Addressing the training needs of the trainers themselves, allowing opportunities for discussion and sharing of best practice
- ▶ Working out at the outset what will be covered by the training, including the level of detail or specialisation of the training
- ▶ Supporting researchers who move between different institutions
- ▶ Providing the training in a timely fashion (for instance, as a means of helping researchers with the formulation of large-scale funding proposals); tailoring the training to the amount of time that researchers can spare – this may be no more than a couple of hours
- ▶ Using training to de-mystify the complexities of legal requirements associated with research data (particularly relevant for biomedical researchers and social scientists). It is important for researchers to appreciate that failure to adhere to certain standards regarding sensitive data could have legal implications

3.20. There are particular challenges around making RDM skills relevant to different disciplinary and institutional communities, and to the standards and cultures reflect them. It is important therefore for trainers to appreciate the varied ways in which data is perceived and defined in a range of contexts; and to adapt the language of RDM so that it is understood by researchers from different disciplines – including the arts and humanities, where the meaning and relevance of data may be especially difficult to grasp. Creating appropriate training resources – this takes time and requires an understanding and knowledge of relevant research environments; knowing which RDM tools are likely to be most useful to researchers, and when and how to use them.

3.21. The documentation of guidance and supporting documentation poses another sort of challenge. A good metadata schema is valuable for helping to identify and find training materials. The EU-funded **FOSTER initiative**¹³ plays that role – but in the longer term, it may not provide a viable option, as it is a finite programme, and it is not clear what happens once it comes to an end. A sustainable resource and entry point is critical, and this is most likely to be provided through an organisation.

Role of different players

3.22. RDM training faces often similar experiences and challenges across borders, but different national frameworks lead to distinct approaches – this has already been touched upon with regards to national strategies (see 3.12). In the UK and Denmark, researchers' behaviour is influenced by the clear requirements set out by funding with regards to RDM and data management planning. But this is less evident in Germany, where funders' expectations are not as stringent – it is interesting to reflect on why some countries are less inclined to implement RDM mandates. In Germany, this may be due to resistance from the research community. In Denmark, by contrast, a bottom-up approach, involving researchers in defining RDM expectations, has helped to get buy-in from them.

3.23. The contrasting national approaches are also reflected by different ways that relevant professional groups, other than researchers, are involved. Here too, it is worth reflecting on national experiences on how RDM is supported by players such as research administrators, finance managers, records managers and archivists.

- ▶ **Research administrators** have a role in RDM because of their responsibilities around the planning and management of research; their further involvement in such areas could help to keep researchers focused on the conducting of research
- ▶ Regarding the involvement of **records managers and archivists**¹⁴, attitudes appear to vary in different KE partner countries. In the UK, for instance, they have had little inclination to be exposed to RDM, and at present generally don't have the right skills to contribute – with the notable exception of The National Archives. In Denmark, on the other hand, archivists are keen to become involved in RDM

These different players have training needs of their own, not least on generic RDM questions to help them develop appropriate infrastructure policies geared to underpin the organisation training effort.

3.24. Learned and professional bodies are a further group of players that can play a vital role in helping to spread RDM practice. They are important influencers of research culture and science policy in their respective spheres, not least through their journals. They provide practical benefits to their members, including supporting career and professional development. They could therefore develop RDM policies and incorporate RDM guidance or training as part of their offer, and thereby contribute to drive researcher behaviour. There are already some instances of learned society involvement that can serve as a precedent. In the UK, the Royal Society has issued guidance on RDM and open data. In the Netherlands, learned societies have approached SURF to develop training courses. Also in the Netherlands, civil engineering societies include RDM in their qualifications – an important incentive. Finally, there is a role also for international learned societies, in areas such as astrophysics, although there is a question mark about whether researchers would consider such bodies an obvious vehicle for skilling and training.

3.25. Arguably, **funding bodies** are the key drivers, because in principle, they are able to require RDM practices. However, in practice, they may not necessarily be in a position to do so: they might not have the expertise to assess compliance, and they face a challenge in devising clear, aligned RDM requirements, particularly at the European level – which is important for applications for EU funding. Furthermore, the success of funders is also dependent on clarity about the ownership of research data. Their mandates may be easier to apply where, as is the case in the Netherlands, they own the data created by the researchers that they fund.

Footnotes

13 FOSTER initiative <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu>

14 It is worth noting that, in March 2016, a month after the workshop, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) set up a new Archives and Records Professionals for Research Data Interest Group <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/archives-records-professionals-for-research-data.html>

Practical ways forward

3.26. From the issues covered during the discussion, a number of considerations emerged about what might be done, practically, to make training more relevant to the professional lives of researchers. In conclusion to the summary of the discussion, these ideas are outlined below.

3.27. How might good RDM practice be encouraged? How might behavioural and cultural change be effected, not just for RDM but more broadly also for open scholarship in general? Carrots are preferable to sticks, and providing incentives and rewards to researchers, including career progression, could be crucial. There is a role there for different players:

- ▶ For **funding bodies**, which could provide tangible feedback or recognition for RDM skills acquired; this might involve strategic funding for RDM
- ▶ For **learned and professional bodies**, representing as they do different research disciplines, and which could also provide incentives – such bodies, not least the more influential ones such as Max Planck and the Royal Society of Chemistry, might address RDM as part of their career and professional development functions
- ▶ For **publishers**, whose high-profile journals could be encouraged to encourage open data and open scholarship

3.28. It makes sense to target PhD students for training, as this helps to embed good RDM practice, for the long term, at the outset of research careers, but there is also a need for buy-in from senior researchers who can play a leadership role.

3.29. There is a case for charting the RDM capabilities of universities, and perhaps even ranking them according to these capabilities – although that would depend on defining a set of accepted criteria, on the basis of the sort of metrics referred to above – see 3.14.

3.30. As an exercise, KE should consider (i) identifying the RDM role – if any – of key professional groups in different national contexts, and (ii) approaching learned societies to assess whether/how their policies and practices have a bearing on RDM.

3.31. KE should also engage with DCC and other relevant organisations to investigate the potential for a sustainable registry of information on training resources, and explore (i) who might host such a registry, and (ii) defining agreed standards and standardised metadata fields for it. Building on existing national initiatives, there is a case to consider international approaches, covering Europe and perhaps beyond.

Annex A: Detailed data from survey responses

For each table, there is an indication of the corresponding figure in section 2 of the report.¹⁵

In which country is your organisation located? (figure 1)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Germany	55.7%	49
Netherlands	15.9%	14
United Kingdom	10.2%	9
Finland	8.0%	7
Denmark	5.7%	5
France	1.1%	1
Greece	1.1%	1
Norway	1.1%	1
Switzerland	1.1%	1
Answered question		88
Skipped question		15

For what subject do you provide training materials? (figure 2)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
General training which is not subject specific	32.0%	33
Life Sciences	20.4%	21
Humanities and Social Sciences	18.5%	19
Natural Sciences	17.5%	18
Engineering Sciences	1.0%	1
Other	10.7%	11
Answered question		103
Skipped question		0

Footnotes

¹⁵ The raw data is accessible at http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6379/13/KE_Training_%26_Skills_Survey_Dec_2015_Raw_data_-_all_responses.xlsx

Do you provide your training materials for a specific type of organisation? If so, please state (multiple responses possible) (figure 3)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
University	59.2%	61
Faculty or department	35.0%	36
Research Organisation	30.1%	31
Open to everyone	28.2%	29
Learned Society or other discipline specific organisation	7.8%	8
Other	10.7%	11
Answered question		103
Skipped question		0

Could you please detail your target audience for your training materials? (multiple responses possible) (figure 4)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
PhD candidates	89.3%	92
Senior researchers (post-docs)	72.8%	75
Graduates	58.3%	60
Professors	47.6%	49
Librarians	37.9%	39
Research administrators / specialised units at university	35.0%	36
Undergraduates	33.0%	34
Data curators	26.2%	27
IT departments /computing centres	20.4%	21
General public	9.7%	10
Other	3.9%	4
Other		103
Skipped question		0

Does your training focus on particular types of data? Please provide us with information on the data types covered by the training you provide. (multiple responses possible) (figure 5)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Training does not focus on particular types of data	65.3%	66
Numbers	30.7%	31
Text	23.8%	24
Images	13.9%	14
Audio	5.9%	6
Video	5.0%	5
Other	13.9%	14
Answered question		101
Skipped question		2

Which phases of the research data lifecycle are covered by your training? (please select all that apply) (figure 6)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
All phases of the Research Data Lifecycle	45.4%	44
Data sharing	43.3%	42
Data preserving	40.2%	39
Data re-using	37.1%	36
Data processing	36.1%	35
Data creation	30.9%	30
Data analysing	29.9%	29
Data protection	26.8%	26
Data anonymization	15.5%	15
Training does not primarily focus on the research data lifecycle	6.2%	6
Don't know	0.0%	0
Other	3.1%	3
Other		97
Skipped question		6

How do you present the training material? (multiple responses possible) (figure 7)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Slides (e.g. part of a lecture)	86.6%	84
Digital format (e.g. pdf files, web pages)	79.4%	77
Printed materials	47.4%	46
Video (e.g. on YouTube)	23.7%	23
Audio (only) (e.g. recorded talk)	7.2%	7
Other	21.6%	21
Answered question		97
Skipped question		6

In which format do you provide your training? (figure 8)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Hands-on training, on-site (e.g. courses at university/institution)	64.9%	63
Both on-site and web-based	27.8%	27
Web-based training (e.g. via skype, youtube or web-based interfaces)	2.1%	2
Other	5.2%	5
Other		97
Skipped question		6

Is your training material freely available on the Internet? (figure 9)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Yes (materials are available for free)	58.7%	54
No (materials can be accessed for a fee)	19.6%	18
Don't know	21.7%	20
Other		92
Skipped question		11

Does the training address applications dedicated to working with data (e.g. DMP-tool, visualisation tool, etc.)? (figure 10)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Yes	57.0%	53
No	34.4%	32
Don't know	8.6%	8
Other		93
Skipped question		25

What is the typical time frame of the training? (Please select all options that apply) (figure 11)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
1-day Workshop	48.4%	46
Block lecture or similar (2-day)	22.1%	21
Summer School or similar (> 2 days)	12.6%	12
Self-pace	11.6%	11
Weekly in a term	10.5%	10
Other	35.8%	34
Answered question		95
Skipped question		8

Who delivers the training? (Please select all that apply) (figure 12)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Data curators or data librarians	54.8%	51
Researchers	44.1%	41
Staff based in research office or department of a university, or a competence centre, or administration, etc.	30.1%	28
Staff based in computing or data centre	29.0%	27
Other	12.9%	12
Other		93
Skipped question		25

What are the main learning objectives of the training? (multiple responses possible) (figure 13)		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Improve knowledge and understanding	89.1%	82
Change practice and/or behaviour	70.7%	65
Skills acquisition	66.3%	61
Influence attitudes and values	54.3%	50
Application awareness building	53.3%	49
Application literacy	23.9%	22
Career progression	14.1%	13
Other	3.3%	3
Other		92
Skipped question		11

How many participants took part in the training offered by your institution/department since 2014? (please provide us with an approximate number) (figure 14)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
< 50 participants	32.1%	27
100 - 199 participants	20.2%	17
50 - 99 participants	19.0%	16
200 - 499 participants	15.5%	13
500+ participants	3.6%	3
Training not yet started	4.8%	4
Don't know	4.8%	4
	Answered question	84
	Skipped question	19

Do you measure a growing interest in the training? (figure 15)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Yes	60.4%	55
No	13.2%	12
Don't know	26.4%	24
	Other	91
	Skipped question	12

Are there specific stakeholders who are especially interested in these training? (please select all that apply) (figure 16a)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Researchers and senior researchers	67.4%	60
Undergraduates and graduates	46.1%	41
Staff based in research office or special departments/units of a university/institution	31.5%	28
Librarians	29.2%	26
Staff based in computer or data centres	13.5%	12
There are no specific groups who are especially interested in these trainings	7.9%	7
Other	10.1%	9
	Other	89
	Skipped question	14

Could you please detail your target audience for your training materials? (multiple responses possible) (figure 16b) – Drawn from question for figure 4, but with categories of stakeholders changed to match those covered in figure 16a. PhD students do not feature in figure 16a, so they have been removed from the comparison.

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Researchers and senior researchers	78.0%	78
Undergraduates and graduates	63.0%	63
Librarians	39.0%	39
Staff based in research office or special departments/units of a university/institution	36.0%	36
Staff based in computer or data centres	21.0%	21
Other	14.0%	14
Answered question		100
Skipped question		0

How is the training evaluated? (figure 17)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Personal feedback (Q&A sessions on-site and online)	34.1%	30
Printed questionnaires	27.3%	24
We do not evaluate the training	15.9%	14
Web questionnaire	14.8%	13
Other	8.0%	7
Other		88
Skipped question		15

What do you perceive as the strengths of the training? (figure 18) – Extrapolation from open-ended responses

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Imparting practical skills	37.5%	24
Raising awareness	29.7%	19
Providing expert advice	23.4%	15
Tailoring to needs	15.6%	10
Promoting relationships/networks	12.5%	8
Understanding principles/theory	7.8%	5
Quality of teaching	3.1%	2
None specified	14.1%	9
Other		64
Skipped question		39

How would you describe the impact of the training? (figure 19) – <i>Extrapolation from open-ended responses</i>		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Awareness-building	40.7%	24
Non-specific impact	20.3%	12
Changes in practices	18.6%	11
Data service visibility	11.9%	7
Changes in behaviour/attitude	8.5%	5
Little/insufficient/no impact	6.8%	4
Network/relationship-building	6.8%	4
Service development	1.7%	1
Too early to say/don't know	10.2%	6
	Answered question	59
	Skipped question	44

Do you feel that there are areas you wish to improve? (figure 20) – <i>Extrapolation from open-ended responses</i>		
Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
Approaches to / presentation of training	29.6%	16
Training for specific tools/applications/methods	22.2%	12
Training for specific disciplines	20.4%	11
Training on particular topics	16.7%	9
Training for particular career stages	7.4%	4
Data infrastructure in the organisation	5.6%	3
All areas	5.6%	3
Few or no areas	5.6%	3
Training on particular data types	1.9%	1
Other	7.4%	4
	Other	54
	Skipped question	49

Please specify the type of organisation you are working for / that is responsible for the training. (multiple answers possible) (figure 21)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
University	62.5%	55
Research organisation	30.7%	27
Library	21.6%	19
Third party funded project	9.1%	8
Computing centre	8.0%	7
Research funder	2.3%	2
Political body	1.1%	1
Other	6.8%	6
Answered question		88
Skipped question		15

How many years has your organisation been involved in delivering training aimed at research data management? (figure 22)

Answer Options	Response percent	Response count
1 - 3 years	32.2%	28
5 - 10 years	18.4%	16
< 1 year	17.2%	15
3 - 5 years	13.8%	12
> 10 years	10.3%	9
Don't know	1.1%	1
Other	6.9%	6
Other		87
Skipped question		16

Annex B: List of workshop participants

First Name	Surname	Organisation
Francis	Andre	CNRS
Libby	Bishop	UK Data Service
Jan	Bot	SURFsara
Tamsin	Burland	Jisc
Bas	Cordewener	Knowledge Exchange
Joy	Davidson	Digital Curation Centre
Arjan	de Wit	Erasmus University Rotterdam University Library
Marlon	Domingus	Erasmus University Rotterdam University Library
Mikael	Elbaek	DTU
Stéphane	Goldstein	InformAll on behalf of Knowledge Exchange
Marjan	Grootveld	DANS
Laurence	Horton	London School of Economics and Political Science
Sarah	James	Knowledge Exchange
Christian	Jämsen	National Institute for Health and Welfare
Matthias	Katerbow	DFG/Knowledge Exchange
Maxi	Kindling	Humboldt-University Berlin
Gareth	Knight	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
Karsten	Kryger Hansen	Aalborg University Library
Ulrich	Meyer-Doeringhaus	German Rectors' Conference
Laura	Molloy	RDA Interest Group on Education and Training on Handling of Research Data
Heike	Neuroth	University of applied sciences Potsdam
Jens	Nieschulze	Georg-August-University Göttingen
Henrik	Pedersen	University of Southern Denmark
Wayne	Peters	King's College London
Rachel	Proudfoot	University of Leeds
Päivi	Rauste	CSC
Jonas	Recker	GESIS
Yvonne	Rommelfanger	Trier University
Fieke	Schoots	Leiden University Library
Isobel	Stark	Southampton University
Adrian	Stevenson	Jisc
Ellen	Verbakel	TU Delft, 3TU Datacentrum
Sven	Vlaeminck	German National Library of Economics
Johanna	Vompras	Bielefeld University
Verena	Weigert	Jisc/Knowledge Exchange

Annex C: Resources described in workshop presentations

Essentials 4 Data Support Course

from Research Data Netherlands, as presented by Ellen Verbakel, Delft University of Technology (see section 3.3)

<http://datasupport.researchdata.nl/en>

RDM training in the social sciences

from Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives (CESSDA), as presented by Jonas Recker, GESIS Data Archive for the Social Sciences, Germany (see section 3.4) –

<http://cessda.net/CESSDA-Training>

Advice and training for research data in the social sciences

from the UK Data Archive, as presented by Libby Bishop, UK Data Service (see section 3.5) –

<http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/advice-training>

RDM training for health researchers

from the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM), as presented by Gareth Knight, LSHTM, United Kingdom (see section 3.6) –

<http://www.lshtm.ac.uk/research/researchdataman/>

Digital Curation Training

from the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), as presented by Joy Davidson, DCC, United Kingdom (see section 3.7)

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/training>

Information Literacy Lens

from the Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF), as outlined during one of the discussion sessions (see section 3.12) –

<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/vitae-publications/rdf-related/information-literacy-lens-on-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework-rdf-apr-2012.pdf/view>

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